

GREEN GROWTH PAVES WAY TO ECONOMIC GROWTH - A MEGA DEVELOPMENT OF SKDRDP THROUGH ITS SELF HELP GROUPS IN KARNATAKA

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Cite This Article: B. Suvarnamalini, "Green Growth Paves Way to Economic Growth - A Mega Development of Skdrdp through Its Self Help Groups in Karnataka", International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Arts and Humanities, Volume 1, Issue 1, Page Number 58-60, 2016.

Abstract:

Shri Kshethra Dharmasthala Rural Development Project (R.) famously called SKDRDP has been promoting sustainable farming practices among small, marginal and micro land holders. Conducive environment in villages have created through formation of Self Help Groups. Poor, backward and weaker sections are empowered socially and economically. In Karnataka 25 districts were covered in farming activities by SKDRDP. Various agricultural and allied activities like horticulture, dairying, floriculture, animal husbandry etc. were undertaken as sources of income. It has contributed towards green growth environment. Even if the developments were related to Karnataka, this paper specially considers Dakshina Kannada District Agro related green growth activities. Based on innovative developments of SKDRDP, suggestions are given which is especially applicable to Dakshina Kannada District.

Key Words: Multiple Cropping, Organic Farming, Non- Conventional Energy, Eco Friendly Environment & Forestry

Introduction:

Karnataka is the eighth largest State in India in terms of geographical size with a population of 6.11crore (as per 2011 census). It is accounted for 5.6% of the geographical area and 5.1 % of the population of India. Nearly 20,842 villages and 320 towns & town panchayaths of 25 districts of Karnataka were covered by SKDRDP through its Self Help Groups. During the year 2014-15, 9.60 lakhs members took up various agricultural and allied activities involving horticulture, dairying, floriculture, animal husbandry, etc. 13,000 farmers were adopted SRI method of paddy cultivation in 13,000 acres of land. A total of 14,300 environment programs, 7,500 watershed programs have been implemented. Organic village concept is implemented in villages of DK, Udupi, and Uttara Kannada districts with the help of Government of Karnataka. Renewable energy is also motivated by SKDRDP. 2,550 gobar gas plants, 10,850 solar home lighting systems were installed by the SKDRDP. A total number of 68,000 sanitation units were constructed during the year by SHG members. Through mass awareness programs, SKDRDP enabled the members to use the sanitation over the project area. All these contributed to the green growth environmental and economic growth.

Objectives:

- ✓ To study the agro based green growth by SKDRDP through Self Help Groups in Karnataka.
- ✓ To examine the economic growth through its micro finance assistance for eco friendly plans.

Limitation:

This study was mainly based on secondary data. But test checking was made through field visits at Madnoor village of Puttur Taluk in Dakshina Kannada District through casual talk with nearly 30 families of Self help Groups.

Contribution of SKDRDP for Green Growth:

Barren land and waste lands are to be converted into green fertile land. Destitute and helpless farmers are neglected in getting financial assistance from commercial banks. Such small and marginal farmers formed a group; prepared farm plans to undertake field activities with the support of sevaprathinidhis of SKDRDP. Agricultural developments contributed towards the green growth of the environment. Organic cultivation in farming practices are eco friendly in nature. Organic farming, Dairy farming, vermi manure plots, jasmine cultivation, SRI method paddy cultivation provided lively hood to the members of Self Help Groups. SKDRDP encouraged more on green growth through these farm developments and non- conventional energy in remote villages.

Farmer members had knowledge of agriculture. Many members were working in the farming for daily and weekly wages. They too had fragmented barren land. These encroached properties were occupied by these persons with huts. With the encouragement of SKDRDP, 8 to 10 persons formed a Self Help Group. As on 30-11-2015, number of active Self Help Groups was 3,20,600 with an active members of 35,83,000. Area of land brought under cultivation was 8,34,000 acres. These developments were made by the SHG members through microfinance programmes of SKDRDP.

Green Growth in Farm Cultivation:

Nearly 23 agro cultivations were taken up by SHGs of SKDRDP. Barren land and waste lands were brought under cultivation. SKDRDP supported in multiple cropping like Areca nut plantation, coconut

plantation, cashew, rubber, banana, coco, beetle, pepper, paddy, vegetables, jasmine and other floriculture etc. It involved many families to become self reliant. All farmers followed organic farming in their cultivation. Outputs of these agricultural developments were the sources of income for the farmers which helped them in timely repayment of their multi number of micro loans. In turn, these innovative agro based economy contributed towards green growth of the country.

Green Growth in Farming Activities:

SKDRDP made barren and waste land into fertile land. Rearing of Cattle, buffalo, goat, pig, hen etc. helped the farmer to keep friendly environment. Green grasses were grown as fodder to the cattle. It keeps the weather cool. Use of vermi compost and waste compost in agricultural field increased the fertility of the soil and yielded heavily. These farming activities also increase the green growth.

Green Growth through Non- Conventional Energy:

SKDRDP encouraged the use of renewable sources in remote villages. Lighting and fuel requirements were fulfilled through these activities. It has given finance to solar home lighting systems and for gobar gas plants installation. It also provided subsidy to meet the cost of gobar gas plants. Till 30-11-2015, installed solar lighting equipment was 41,438 and gobar gas system 22,169. These sources of energy are environment friendly and economic for the use of needy members. More encouragement to non- conventional energy removes the burden on the environment.

Green Growth in Sanitation for Better Environment:

SKDRDP has taken up one house one toilet programme. It created sanitation awareness among the people and has given incentives ranging Rs. 500 to Rs. 1,000 for constructing toilets. As on 30-11-2015, number of toilets constructed was 2,65,000. Open ground used for toilet activities pollutes the environment. Sanitation was supported by the village people considerably.

Green Growth in Environment Protection:

SKDRDP has conducted several programmes on social forestry, water conservation, drinking water supply etc. Planting the sapling of trees, fruit trees, medicinal plants were supplied by conducting village and school programmes. Large number of agro related plants were planted. Plants were developed in each and every place where people supported in community developments in the form of forestry.

Green Growth through Watershed Development Programmes:

SKDRDP has conducted programmes on rain water harvesting and water management activities also. Water conservation, optimum use of rain water, watershed methodology, and community oriented watershed activities were undertaken. More number of families was involved in percolation of pits, farm ponds, bunding, quarry filling and bore well recharging. They were interested in collecting more water in one or the other form. Thus watershed developments too helped in keeping green environment.

Financial Support of SKDRDP for Green Growth:

Micro finance support was given to the needy members. Financial assistance was given for garbage and manure composting, watershed, sanitation and environmental activities in addition to other requirements of the members. It shows that SKDRDP has made a lot of efforts in green growth of the environment. Numerous numbers of loans were sanctioned to various eco developmental activities. With its micro finance assistance to its SHGs needy members Agricultural Development, Irrigation, Housing and sanitation, Livelihood and other activities were undertaken.

Suggestions on Green Growth with Special Concern to Dakshina Kannada District:

- ✓ Encourage to develop Coconut, Areca Industries. Production of tender coconut water juice, coconut shell powder, coconut shell carbon, broomsticks of dried coconut leaves, coconut coir based items like ropes and nets are to be supported. Areca nut is a major commercial crop which can be raw material for supari making and its wastes can be used to preserve water while growing vegetables. Areca plant leaves can be used to make plates, bowls etc.
- ✓ Seasonal fruits such as Mango, Jackfruit, Papaya, Pineapple and Banana are available in plenty. Fruit processing units based on these fruits are to be developed. Natural fruit extracts are good to health and environment friendly.
- ✓ Fish cultivation in ponds and underground water tank areas can be used as a source of revenue.
- ✓ Floriculture in the form of Jasmine cultivation is to be encouraged. Weather of this area suits to it. It was proved at Kavu in Madnoor village by a SHG member.
- ✓ Botanical and medicinal related plants are useful in ayurvedic medicines. On the other side, it is environment friendly.
- ✓ Cattle, goat, pig, poultry farming generates compost and manure. Likewise, Kitchen waste can be used for bio- gas and fertilization. These can be an additional source of income to a farmer.
- ✓ Tree based park developments are to be made to give awareness about the green growth.
- ✓ Agro based pesticides and insecticides can be developed with the help of Desi cow dung and urine with neem and other related leaves.
- ✓ Agricultural wastes can be used as fodder to the cattle and as bedding for growing vegetables.

- ✓ Go by walk, ride bicycle, use public transport like bus and train for long journey to save our earth.

Conclusion:

Go Green, Think Green, and Act Green so that an earth can Live Green and be Evergreen. It was implemented and proved by SKDRDP in villages through SHG members. Poor and marginal members became happy with green family by taking the assistance of micro finance. It contributed towards economic growth and developed eco friendly environment. Now everyone has to act green to reach our goal. Let all of us have a Green Garden with Evergreen Energy.

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